

New record of *Pyrgopolon ctenactis* (Annelida: Serpulidae) in Manzanillo, Colima, Mexican Pacific

Nuevo registro de *Pyrgopolon ctenactis* (Annelida: Serpulidae) en Manzanillo, Colima, Pacífico mexicano

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ABSTRACT

This study provides the first record of the serpulid worm *Pyrgopolon ctenactis* in Manzanillo, Colima, Mexico. The worms were found attached to a sunken ship hull and rocky substrate at 5–7 m depth. A full description and images of diagnostic structures are included.

Key words: *Sclerostyla*, Manzanillo Port, tubeworm, serpulid, ship hull, harbor biota

RESUMEN

Este estudio proporciona el primer registro del gusano serpúlido *Pyrgopolon ctenactis* en Manzanillo, Colima, México. Los gusanos fueron encontrados adheridos a las paredes de un barco hundido y en sustrato rocoso, entre 5 y 7 metros de profundidad. Se incluye una descripción completa e imágenes de estructuras diagnósticas.

Palabras clave: *Sclerostyla*, Puerto de Manzanillo, gusanos tubícolas, serpúlidos, casco de barco, biota de puertos.

INTRODUCTION

The genus *Pyrgopolon* de Montfort, 1808 includes one fossil taxon and three recent species of serpulid worms with an operculum and a peduncle entirely calcified (ten Hove & Kupriyanova, 2009). One of these species is *Pyrgopolon ctenactis*, described by Mörch (1863) from Saint Thomas, Lesser Antilles as *Serpula* (*Sclerostyla*) *ctenactis*. The revision by ten Hove (1973) includes detailed drawings of chaetae, uncini, and operculae of *P. ctenactis*, as well as a full description, including tube morphology. *Pyrgopolon ctenactis* have ampho-American records, in the Caribbean and the Tropical American Pacific (ten Hove 1973, ten Hove & Kupriyanova, 2009).

Abbreviations: LEMA: Colección Biológica del Laboratorio de Ecosistemas Marinos y Acuicultura, Universidad de Guadalajara, México.

RESULTS

Systematics

Serpulidae Rafinesque, 1815

Pyrgopolon de Montfort, 1808

Pyrgopolon ctenactis (Mörch, 1863)

Figures 1–3

Serpula (*Sclerostyla*) *ctenactis* Mörch, 1863: 386, type locality: St. Thomas, Lesser Antilles. *Sclerostyla ctenactis*.– Bush, 1905: 224 (type designation).

Placostegus calciferus Treadwell, 1929: 12–13, figs. 34–36 (Puerto Rico, *vide* ten Hove, 1973). *Sclerostyla ctenactis*.– ten Hove, 1973: 6–12, figs. 1–4, 7, 20–31, pls. 1, 3a–b, 3, 7 (Curaçao, Bonaire, Klein Bonaire, St. Thomas, Puerto Rico, Tortugas, Honduras, Panamá, West Indies, Colombia).– de León-González, 1990: 335–336, fig. 2 a–f (Punta San Juanico and Cabo San Lorenzo, Baja California Sur).– de León-González et al. 1993: 879 (Puerto Escondido Bay, Baja California Sur).

Pyrgopolon ctenactis.– Jäger, 1993: 95 (new combination, synonymy of the genera *Sclerostyla* Mörch and *Heptervis* Regenhardt with *Pyrgopolon*).– Bastida-Zavala, 2008: 42, figs 10A–D (Baja California Sur, Guerrero and Oaxaca).– Pillai, 2009: 53, fig. 3 (Bonaire).– Bastida-Zavala et al. 2016: 432–433, fig. 13D (Oaxaca).– Galván-Villa et al. 2023: supplementary table 2 (S2) (Colima).

Material examined. San Luciano shipwreck, Santiago Bay, Colima (19°06'25"N, 104°23'46"W), July 27, 2021, one specimen, 5 m depth, sunken ship hull (LEMA-PO175, M212); San Pedrito, Manzanillo Bay, Colima (19°03'33"N, 104°18'16"W), July 28, 2021, one specimen, 7 m depth, rocks (LEMA-PO176, M256); San Luciano shipwreck, Santiago Bay, Colima (19°06'25"N, 104°23'46"W), January 18, 2022, one specimen, 6 m depth, sunken ship hull (LEMA-PO177, M551).

Description. Tubes lost. Life color: radiolar crown with red and white alternate bands. Opercular base bright red. Bright red compound eyespots near the anterior opercular margin. Body cream colored. A greenish, ventral, triangular pad in thorax. Whitish, rectangular, abdominal shields (Fig. 1A). Two specimens incomplete, lacking most posterior segments (M212 and M551), and one complete (M256). Body length, from the tip of opercula to pygidium: 13–16 mm. Body width at mid-thorax: 3.2–4.6 mm. Radiolar crown length: 2.5–5 mm. Radioles arranged in two semi-circles (Figs. 1A, 2A). Right lobe with 23–29 radioles. Radioles united by inter-radiolar membrane for 1/4 of their length. Radioles without eyes. Pinnulae extends along the entire radiolar length. Operculum and peduncle entirely calcified (Figs. 1A–C), enclosed by thin fleshy layer of soft tissue; in specimen M212 it is broken forming a flap (Fig. 2A–B, E–F). Operculum funnel-shaped (Fig. 1C, E), with 17 radial, granulose ridges on inner side (Fig. 1D, F) and 17 triangular marginal spines (some broken or damaged). A circle of compound eyespots near the anterior opercular margin (around the brim of the operculum) (Figs. 1A, C, G, 2E, 3B). Peduncle inserted medially (Figs. 1C, 2F). Base of peduncle pear-shaped (Figs. 1C, 2F). Peduncle 0.5–0.8 mm width. Peduncle length 4–5.3 mm. Operculum length: 2–4 mm. Peduncle with 4 longitudinal grooves running through peduncular length: dorsal (Fig. 3D), ventral (Fig. 3E) and two lateral (Fig. 3F). Operculum diameter: 2.6–3.8 mm. Operculum of specimen M256 as basibiont of another serpulid worm, tube empty, probably of *Hydroides* genus (Fig. 3A, C). Pseudoperculum absent. Six thoracic chaetigers in all specimens (no collar chaetae were seen). Ventral margin of collar entire (Fig. 1A). Thoracic membrane wide anteriorly, narrowing at 3rd (M551) or 4rd segment (M212, M256) (Fig. 2B), united ventrally on first abdominal segment forming a short, reminiscent apron (Figs. 1A–B, 2A). Thoracic chaetae limbate, narrowly hooded (Fig. 3G–H). Thoracic uncini saw-shaped, with 9–

10 teeth (Fig. 3J, L), anterior peg bluntly truncated, indented anteriorly. Thoracic tori almost touching ventrally in posterior thoracic segments, leaving a clear triangular depression (Figs. 1A–B, 2A). Abdominal chaetigers: 44 in the complete specimen (M256). First abdominal chaetigers emerged from oval lobes or tonguelets located in middle of trunk (Fig. 2B–D), following chaetigers displaces gradually towards lateral sides of the body (Fig. 2C–D). Abdominal chaetae capillary, with short hollow trumpet-shaped tips (Fig. 3I). Abdominal uncini rasp-shaped with 7–8 teeth in profile (Fig. 3K, M), two in a row. Achaetous anterior abdominal zone present (Fig. 2B). Short capillary chaetae present posteriorly. Glandular pad absent.

Fig. 1. *Pyrgopolon ctenactis* (Mörch, 1863), LEMA-PO177 (M551). A. Entire worm, ventral side, life color. B. Same, post-fixed color. C. Operculum and peduncle, dorsal side. D, F. Operculum, frontal view. E. Operculum ventral side. G. Detail of opercular eyes and sharply pointed teeth. Scale bars: A–B, 4 mm; C, 0.7 mm; D, 3.5 mm; E, 0.7 mm; F, 3.5 mm; G, 0.3 mm.

Fig. 2. *Pyrgopolon ctenactis* (Mörch, 1863) with operculum partially broken, LEMA-PO175 (M212). A. Entire worm, ventral side. B. Same, dorsal side. C. Abdomen, dorsal side. D. Detail of first abdominal chaetigers, dorsal view. E. Remaining soft tissue showing eyes. F. Operculum, dorsal side. Scale bars: A–B, 4 mm; C, 2 mm; D, 2.7 mm; E–F, 1 mm. Stained with Shirlastain-A.

Fig. 3. *Pyrgopolon ctenactis* (Mörch, 1863) with operculum as basibiont of another serpulid worm, LEMA- PO176 (M256). A. Operculum, dorsal view. B. Same, ventral view. C. Epibiont serpulid above the operculum of *P. ctenactis*, apical view. D. Peduncular groove, dorsal side. E. Same, ventral side. F. Same, lateral side. G. Thoracic chaetiger 2. H. Detail of limbate chaetae in G. I. Abdominal capillary chaetae. J–K. Thoracic uncini from chaetiger 3. L–M. Uncini from middle abdomen. Scale bars: A, D–F, 0.5 mm; B–C, 2.5 mm; G, I, 40 x magnification; H, J–K, L–M, 400 x magnification. Epibiont serpulid, empty tube was removed during manipulation (not shown in D–F).

Remarks. The opercular shape is very similar to those reported by ten Hove (1973), Bastida-Zavala (2008) and Pillai (2009), except for the following differences. ten Hove (1973) illustrate the base of peduncle discretely swollen (ten Hove, 1973; Fig. 31) whereas specimens here reported from Manzanillo have peduncular bases pear-shaped: a rounded base becoming triangular toward upside (Figs. 1C, 2F, this study) as well as in Pillai (2009: Fig. 3).

Bastida-Zavala (2008) reported the presence of a large thoracic membrane, extending to the 7th thoracic chaetiger and forming ventral apron. Specimens here examined from Manzanillo have thoracic membranes extending to 3rd (one specimen) or 4rd segment (two specimens) forming a very short apron.

DISCUSSION

As already emphasized by ten Hove (1973), the difficulty to study species of *Pyrgopolon* is due to their rarity and their tube is usually imbedded in the substrate. In addition, tubes are often removed from the body by technicians when first sorted, and it is not preserved for further study. Besides, opercula are often covered with several epibionts, making difficult its cleaning, or causing its rupture and damage of opercular ornamentations.

Except for the contribution by Pillai (2009) who analysed the opercular insertion and their zoogeography, phylogeny of the *Pyrgopolon* species have never been studied. There are some available sequences of *P. ctenactis* at the National Center for Biotechnology Information (OQ412625.1, OQ389673.1, OQ3794441.1) (NCBI, 2024), but at this time it is not possible to confirm whether *Pyrgopolon ctenactis* constitute same genetic species on both coasts of America or not, since specimens reported previously from the Mexican Pacific and those from the present study were preserved with formaldehyde and, after a short period, transferred to ethanol.

In the Mexican Pacific *Pyrgopolon ctenactis* has been reported adhered to rocks and coral off Punta San Juanico and Cabo San Lazaro (Western coast of Baja California Sur) at 27–30 m depth (de León-González, 1990). Also reported in Puerto Escondido, Baja California Sur (Gulf of California) on the spiny oysters *Spondylus princeps unicolor* at 30 m depth (de León-González et al. 1993); on *Spondylus calcifer* (now recognized as *S. limbatus*) (Bastida-Zavala, 2008); on *Spondylus limbatus* (Bastida-Zavala et al. 2016); and on the sea snails *Muricanthus*, also among rock, kelp, and crevices filled with boulders (Bastida-Zavala, 2008). This study reports *Pyrgopolon ctenactis* for the first time in artificial substrate, a sunken ship hull as well as a rocky substrate.

The revision by ten Hove (1973) still remains the most comprehensive source of information from the genus *Pyrgopolon*.

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